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No G6PD A- (G202A) variant detected among *Plasmodium falciparum*-positive patients in Awka, Southeast Nigeria: a hospital-based study

Moses Ikegbunam^{1,2*}, Nwokike Uchechukwu³, Harrison Abone¹, Ani Ezinne Grace⁴, Mercy Ezeunala⁵, Nnanna Joy⁶, Nzeukwu Chibumma Immaculata⁴, Joy Ogugua Igwe⁷, Obiageli Okeke⁸, Frances Nworji⁹, Peter Ihekwereme³

1 Department of Pharmaceutical Microbiology and Biotechnology, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Science, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria. 2 Molecular Research Foundation for students and scientists, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. 3 Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria. 4 Department of Parasitology and Entomology, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. 5 National Institute for Pharmaceutical Research and Development (NIPRD), Idu, Abuja, Nigeria. 6 Department of Biological Sciences (Microbiology Unit), Dennis Osadabay University, Asaba Delta State. 7 Department of Pharmaceutical microbiology and Biotechnology, Faculty of Pharmaceutical Science, Abia state University, Uturu, Abia State. 8 Department of Zoology, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria. 9 Department of Applied Biochemistry, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria. *email: mn.ikegbunam@unizik.edu.ng

Background: Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) deficiency, prevalent in malaria-endemic regions, has been associated with a reduced risk of severe malaria due to impaired parasite growth in deficient erythrocytes. The G6PD gene, located on the X chromosome, harbours various mutations associated with differing enzyme activity levels. This study investigates the prevalence of G6PD deficiency variants and their impact on parasite density and haemoglobin levels among malaria-positive patients in Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria.

Materials and Methods: Blood samples were collected from 100 malaria positive participants; 64 participants with complete genotyping and clinical data were included in the analysis and screened for the A376G and G202A variants using PCR and Sanger sequencing.

Results: Molecular analysis indicated that the B variant (normal) was predominant, with 83% of the participants possessing this variant. None of the participants tested had the A- variant, associated with G6PD deficiency, suggesting no evidence of the G202A (A-) variant in this hospital-based sample. The B variant and the A+ variant showed no significant impact on the haemoglobin and parasitaemia levels of the study participants.

Conclusions: The findings support the absence of the G202A (A-) variant in this cohort and show no detectable differences in parasitaemia or haemoglobin between A+ and B genotypes. Broader genotyping and/or G6PD enzyme activity testing in community representative samples is recommended before drawing population-level conclusions or informing treatment policy.

INTRODUCTION

Malaria is a major public health problem across many tropical and subtropical regions worldwide, with the highest burden in sub-Saharan Africa. Evolutionary pressure from malaria has shaped the frequency of host genetic polymorphisms affecting red blood cell biology, which may modify the risk of severe malaria infections [1]. One of the most common inherited factors is Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) deficiency, characterised by reduced enzyme activity and an X-linked inheritance pattern [2,3]. The geographical distribution of G6PD deficiency overlaps with malaria endemicity, suggesting a possible selective advantage, although

the underlying protective mechanisms remain incompletely understood [3,4].

G6PD deficiency confers both potential advantages and risks in the context of malaria. Individuals with G6PD deficiency have been reported to exhibit lower parasite densities and a reduced risk of severe malaria in some settings. However, deficiency also predisposes to oxidative stress-induced haemolysis, triggering onset of acute haemolytic anaemia [5,6]. This is particularly relevant for 8-aminoquinoline antimalarials such as primaquine, used to target *Plasmodium vivax/ovale* hypnozoites and gametocytes, because these drugs can cause dose-dependent oxidative haemolysis in patients with G6PD deficiency [5,6].

The G6PD gene exhibits considerable allelic diversity, with over 200 variants associated with suboptimal enzyme activity [7]. In sub-Saharan Africa, three predominant variants B, A, and A-display varying levels of enzyme activity, with implications for malaria outcomes [5]. While the A-variant has been linked to protection against malaria, the extent of this protection varies across different studies [5]. Other endemic regions feature distinct G6PD variants, such as G6PD Mediterranean [1,2] and G6PD Mahidol [5,8], which have also been associated with malaria-related phenotypes.

This study elucidated the prevalence of G6PD genotypes in Awka, Anambra State, and explored their influence on malaria parasite density and haemoglobin levels among malaria-positive patients. Examining the relationship between genetic factors and malaria parameters will contribute to a deeper understanding of malaria pathogenesis and inform strategies for disease management in endemic regions. Importantly, because this is a hospital-based, malaria-positive cohort, the study evaluated associations within cases and does not directly estimate infection risk ('susceptibility') in the general population.

METHODOLOGY

The study to determine the allelic diversity of G6PD genotypes and its effect on parasitaemia and haemoglobin concentration in malaria patients in Awka, Anambra State was carried out at the Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu Teaching Hospital (COOUTH), Awka, Anambra State, between July 2019 and November 2020. Awka is a metropolis in Anambra State, Southeastern Nigeria with an estimated population of 244,005 [9].

Study population

Blood samples were collected from 100 participants infected with malaria, as confirmed by RDT. Appropriate ethical approval and parental consent for children who participated in the study were obtained. Participants were randomly selected, with 36 males and 64 females participating in the study. Of these, 64 participants with complete genotyping and haemoglobin/parasitaemia data were included in the final analysis.

Parasite counts

Parasite density was determined on Giemsa-stained thick blood films by a WHO-certified malaria microscopist immediately after sample collection. Thick films were prepared, air dried, and stained with 10% Giemsa for 10 min. Microscopy was performed using a light microscope with a 100× oil immersion objective. Asexual parasites were counted against 200 white blood cells (WBCs), and parasite density was estimated using an assumed WBC count. Parasite density (parasites/ μ l) was calculated as:

$$\text{Parasites}/\mu\text{l} = (\text{Number of parasites counted} \times 8,000) / 200$$

where 8,000 WBC/ μ l was used as the assumed WBC count for all participants. Parasite density values were recorded as parasites/ μ l and used for subsequent analyses.

Haemoglobin concentration

Haemoglobin concentration was measured at the point of blood collection using a HemoCue® photometer (HemoCue AB, Ängelholm, Sweden). Briefly, fresh whole blood was collected and a small volume was introduced into a HemoCue microcuvette according to the manufacturer's instructions. The filled microcuvette was inserted into the photometer for photometric determination of haemoglobin concentration, and results were recorded immediately in g/dL. The device was operated with routine quality control in line with the manufacturer's recommendations, including verification with the instrument's built in self-check and/or control cuvettes where available.

G6PD Genotyping and sequencing

Genomic DNA was extracted from blood samples using the Quick-DNA Miniprep Plus Kit (Zymo Research) from 200 μ l of blood according to the manufacturer's protocol. The polymorphic region of the G6PD gene was genotyped by polymerase chain reaction (PCR). In the PCR reaction, 3 μ l of the extracted DNA was amplified in a 25 μ l reaction consisting of 12.5 μ l of One Taq Quick-Load 2X Master Mix (New England Biolabs Inc.), 0.5 μ l of

forward (5'-GCCCCTGTGACCTCCCGCCA-3') and reverse (5'-GCAACGGCAAGCCTTACATCTGG-3') primers, and 8.5 µl of nuclease-free water. The amplification conditions include an initial denaturation step at 94°C for 5 min, followed by 35 cycles of denaturation at 94°C for 45 seconds, primer annealing step at 65°C for 1 min, and strand extension at 72°C for 1 min. This was followed by a final extension at 72°C for 5 min. The PCR products were resolved on a 1.5% agarose gel stained with Ethidium Bromide. The results were viewed using a UV transilluminator.

Subsequently, the PCR products were purified using Exosap (Exo-SAP-IT, USB, Affymetrix, USA), according to the manufacturer's protocol. The purified product was then used as a template for DNA sequencing by Eurofins MGW. G6PD polymorphisms were identified by comparing the sequencing results with the G6PD reference sequence gene (NG_009015.2) using the Codoncode Aligner 4.0 software (<http://www.codoncode.com>).

Statistical analysis

All data were analysed using GraphPad Prism software, version 10.1.2. Data were grouped according to G6PD variation. Descriptive statistics were determined. The association of G6PD varia-

tion and parasitaemia or haemoglobin profiles, in males and females, respectively, was analysed using an unpaired t-test or Mann-Whitney U test, as appropriate based on data distribution. Statistical significance was considered at a p-value < 0.05. Given the small number of A+ males (n=2), genotype stratified comparisons in males should be interpreted as exploratory.

Ethical clearance

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the Institutional Review Board/Ethics Committee of Chukwuemeka Odimegwu Ojukwu Teaching Hospital, Awka, Nigeria (COOUTH/CMAC/ETH.C/Vol.1/0035).

RESULTS

Overall, 64 of the 100 malaria patients who enrolled in this study were included in the analysis. Female malaria patients constituted 67% (n=43) of the study population while 33% (n=21) of the study participants were male. The average (\pm SD) age of the female (range 1-44 yrs) and male (range 12-42 yrs) participants was 24.49 ± 9.22 and 22.95 ± 7.48 , respectively. The parasitaemia and haemoglobin

Figure 1. Parasitaemia (left) and haemoglobin levels (right) in study participants

levels of study participants are shown in Figure 1. Participants included were those with complete genotyping and clinical data.

Prevalence of G6PD variants

PCR and subsequent genome sequence analysis showed the presence of the B (376A/202G) and A+ (376G/202G) variants at the assayed loci (Table 1). The B variant was predominant in both females (79.07%) and males (90.48%). None of the participants tested carried the A- (202A) variant; all participants were 202G at the assayed position. Among females, genotypes at the A376G locus were called as either 376A/376A or 376G/376G; no heterozygous (376A/376G) calls were observed in this dataset.

Gender	G6PD Variants			
	B (376A)	A+ (376G)	N (202G)	A- (202A)
Male	19 (90.48%)	2 (9.52%)	21(100%)	0
Female	34 (79.07%)	9 (20.93%)	43(100%)	0

Table 1. G6PD variants in study participants. N designates the normal polymorphism at position

Effect of G6PD genotype on parasitaemia levels in patients

G6PD A+ and B genotypes showed no significant impact on the parasitaemia profile of male and female subjects (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Scatter plot showing the relationship between G6PD genotype and parasitaemia.

Effect of G6PD genotype on haemoglobin level

Analysis of the haemoglobin profiles of malaria patients with either the G6PD B or A+ genotype

(Figure 3) showed that there was no significant effect of G6PD genotypes (A+, B) on the haematological profiles both male ($p = 0.95$) and female ($p = 0.64$) subjects.

Figure 3. Scatter Plot showing relationship between G6PD genotype and haemoglobin.

DISCUSSION

In this hospital-based cohort of malaria positive patients in Awka, we detected only the B (376A/202G) and A+ (376G/202G) variants at the assayed loci, and no participant carried the G202A (A-) allele. This observation should be interpreted as absence of G202A in this sample rather than an estimate of population prevalence.

Absence of the G202A allele among malaria patients has been reported in some African settings, including studies from Ethiopia [12,13] highlighting geographic heterogeneity in G6PD variants. In addition, because we genotyped only two loci (A376G and G202A), other deficiency associated alleles could be present but undetected; therefore, broader genotyping and/or phenotypic testing is required to characterise local G6PD deficiency comprehensively.

Because G6PD is X-linked, males are typically either normal or hemizygous deficient, whereas females may be homozygous or heterozygous. Random X-chromosome inactivation in heterozygous females results in red blood cell mosaicism and a wide range of measured enzyme activity. This biology reduces the sensitivity of qualitative point-of-care G6PD tests in females and increases the risk of misclassification around clinically relevant thresholds [14,23-25]. These considerations

support WHO-recommended G6PD testing prior to primaquine based radical cure and underscore the value of combining genotyping with quantitative enzyme activity testing when evaluating local risk [3,14].

In this dataset, the mildly deficient A+ genotype was not associated with parasitaemia or haemoglobin compared with the B genotype. Interpretation of male subgroup comparisons is limited by the very small number of A+ males (n=2). The absence of heterozygous calls among females at the A376G locus is unusual for an X-linked trait and may reflect limited sample size, selection of malaria-positive hospital attendees, or technical/genotype-calling constraints; female genotype proportions are therefore interpreted cautiously. Prior studies have reported variable associations between G6PD genotypes and parasite density, with more consistent effects often observed for intermediate or severe deficiency variants rather than A+ [19,20].

Overall, our findings indicate that within this malaria-positive cohort, no G202A (A-) variant was detected and no association was observed between A+ and parasitaemia or haemoglobin. Larger community representative studies incorporating broader genotyping and quantitative G6PD enzyme activity testing are warranted to estimate population prevalence and to inform safe use of 8-aminoquinolines, which may precipitate acute haemolytic anaemia in G6PD-deficient individuals [3,5,6,15].

Limitations

This was a hospital-based, malaria-positive cohort; therefore, the study assesses associations among cases and does not directly estimate malaria infection risk ('susceptibility') in the general population. Only two G6PD loci (A376G and G202A) were genotyped, which does not capture the full allelic diversity of G6PD variants in West Africa; absence of G202A in this cohort should not be interpreted as absence of G6PD deficiency overall. Enzyme activity was not measured, and genotype phenotype correspondence particularly in females because of X-chromosome inactivation cannot be inferred from these data alone. In addition, qualitative point-of-care tests can misclassify heterozygous females due to mosaicism. Finally, the small number of A+ males limited statistical power for subgroup com-

parisons, and the absence of heterozygous calls among females should be interpreted cautiously.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, among the malaria-positive patients analysed in this hospital-based study, no evidence of the G6PD G202A (A-) variant was detected in Awka, Anambra State. The A+ variant showed no detectable association with parasitaemia or haemoglobin when compared with the B variant in this dataset. Larger, community-representative studies that combine broader genotyping with G6PD enzyme activity testing are recommended before drawing population level conclusions or informing treatment policy where G6PD status is relevant.

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COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors report no competing interests.

REFERENCES

1. Grant AV, Roussilhon C, Paul R, Sakuntabhai A: The genetic control of immunity to *Plasmodium* infection. *BMC Immunol.* 2015, **16**: 14. [Doi: 10.1186/s12865-015-0078-z](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12865-015-0078-z)
2. Beutler E: Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase deficiency: a historical perspective. *Blood* 2008, **111**: 16–24. [Doi: 10.1182/blood-2007-04-077412](https://doi.org/10.1182/blood-2007-04-077412)
3. Domingo GJ, Satyagraha AW, Anvikar A, Baird K *et al.*: G6PD testing in support of treatment and elimination of malaria: recommendations for evaluation of G6PD tests. *Malar. J.* 2013, **12**: 391. [Doi: 10.1186/1475-2875-12-391](https://doi.org/10.1186/1475-2875-12-391)
4. Awab GR, Aaram F, Jamornthanyawat N, Suwannasin K *et al.*: Protective effect of Mediterranean-type glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase deficiency against *Plasmodium vivax* malaria. *eLife* 2021, **10**: e62448. [Doi: 10.7554/eLife.62448](https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.62448)
5. Amoah LE, Asare KK, Dickson D, Abankwa J *et al.*: Genotypic glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) deficiency protects against *Plasmodium falciparum* infection in individuals living

- in Ghana. *PLoS One* 2021, **16**: e0257562. [Doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0257562](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0257562)
6. Bancone G, Chu CS, Somsakchaicharoen R, Chowwiwat N *et al.*: Characterization of G6PD Genotypes and Phenotypes on the Northwestern Thailand-Myanmar Border. *PLoS One* 2014, **9**: e116063. [Doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0116063](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0116063)
 7. Boonyuen U, Songdej D, Tanyaratsrisakul S, Phuanukoonnon S *et al.*: Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase mutations in malaria endemic area of Thailand by multiplexed high-resolution melting curve analysis. *Malar. J.* 2021, **20**: 194. [Doi: 10.1186/s12936-021-03731-0](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12936-021-03731-0)
 8. Bharti RS, Vashisht K, Ahmed N, Nayak A *et al.*: First report of glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) variants (Mahidol and Acores) from malaria-endemic regions of northeast India and their functional evaluations in-silico. *Acta Trop.* 2020, **202**: 105252. [Doi: 10.1016/j.actatropica.2019.105252](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actatropica.2019.105252)
 9. Mbah S, Ejike N, Mgbemena G: Urban Poverty Incidence in Nigeria: A study of Awka metropolis Anambra State, Nigeria. *Int. J. Business Soc. Sci.* 2016, **7**, 5. <https://tinyurl.com/5ex5kva7> (Accessed 3 January 2026).
 10. Howes RE, Piel FB, Patil AP, Nyangiri OA *et al.*: G6PD deficiency prevalence and estimates of affected populations in malaria endemic countries: A Geostatistical model-based map. *PLoS Med.* 2012, **9**: e1001339. [Doi: 10.1371/journal.pmed.1001339](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1001339)
 11. Da Rocha JEB, Othman H, Tiemessen CT, Botha G *et al.*: G6PD distribution in sub-Saharan Africa and potential risks of using chloroquine/hydroxychloroquine based treatments for COVID-19. *Pharmacogenomics J.* 2021, **21**: 649–656. [Doi: 10.1038/s41397-021-00242-8](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41397-021-00242-8)
 12. Carter TE, Mekonnen SK, Lopez K, Bonnell V *et al.*: Glucose-6-Phosphate Dehydrogenase deficiency genetic variants in malaria patients in Southwestern Ethiopia. *Am. J. Trop. Med. Hyg.* 2017, **98**: 83–87. [Doi: 10.4269/ajtmh.17-0557](https://doi.org/10.4269/ajtmh.17-0557)
 13. Assefa A, Ali A, Deressa W, Tsegaye W *et al.*: Glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) deficiency in Ethiopia: absence of common African and Mediterranean allelic variants in a nationwide study. *Malar. J.* 2018, **17**: 388. [Doi: 10.1186/s12936-018-2538-4](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12936-018-2538-4)
 14. Chu CS, Bancone G, Kelley M, Advani N *et al.*: Optimizing G6PD testing for *Plasmodium vivax* case management and beyond: why sex, counseling, and community engagement matter. *Wellcome Open Res.* 2020, **5**: 21. [Doi: 10.12688/wellcomeopenres.15700.2](https://doi.org/10.12688/wellcomeopenres.15700.2)
 15. Yang HC, Wu YH, Yen WC, Liu HY, Hwang TL, Stern A, *et al.*: The Redox Role of G6PD in Cell Growth, Cell Death, and Cancer. *Cells.* 2019 Sep;8(9):1055.
 16. Brito-Sousa JD, Peixoto HM, Devine A, Silva-Neto AV *et al.*: Real-life quantitative G6PD screening in *Plasmodium vivax* patients in the Brazilian Amazon: A cost-effectiveness analysis. *PLoS Negl. Trop. Dis.* 2022, **16**: e0010325. [Doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0010325](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0010325)
 17. Pfeffer DA, Satyagraha AW, Sadhewa A, Alam MS *et al.*: Genetic variants of Glucose-6-Phosphate Dehydrogenase and their associated enzyme activity: A systematic review and meta-Analysis. *Pathogens* 2022, **11**: 1045. [Doi: 10.3390/pathogens11091045](https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens11091045)
 18. Luzzatto L: G6PD deficiency: a polymorphism balanced by heterozygote advantage against malaria. *Lancet Haematol.* 2015, **2**: e400–1. [Doi: 10.1016/s2352-3026\(15\)00191-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2352-3026(15)00191-x)
 19. Khammanee T, Sawangjaroen N, Buncherd H, Tun AW *et al.*: Prevalence of Glucose-6-Phosphate Dehydrogenase (G6PD) deficiency among malaria patients in Southern Thailand: 8 Years retrospective study. *Korean J. Parasitol.* 2022, **60**: 15–23. [Doi: 10.3347/kjp.2022.60.1.15](https://doi.org/10.3347/kjp.2022.60.1.15)
 20. Dewasurendra RL, Rockett KA, Fernando SD, Carter R *et al.*: G6PD gene variants and its association with malaria in a Sri Lankan population. *Malar. J.* 2015, **14**: 93. [Doi: 10.1186/s12936-015-0603-9](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12936-015-0603-9)
 21. Clark TG, Fry AE, Auburn S, Campino S *et al.*: Allelic heterogeneity of G6PD deficiency in West Africa and severe malaria susceptibility. *Eur. J. Hum. Genet.* 2009, **17**: 1080–1085. [Doi: 10.1038/ejhg.2009.8](https://doi.org/10.1038/ejhg.2009.8)
 22. Rockett KA, Clarke GM, Fitzpatrick K, Hubbart C *et al.*: Reappraisal of known malaria resistance loci in a large multicenter study. *Nat. Genet.* 2014, **46**: 1197–1204. [Doi: 10.1038/ng.3107](https://doi.org/10.1038/ng.3107)
 23. Satyagraha AW, Sadhewa A, Baramuli V, Elvira R *et al.*: G6PD Deficiency at Sumba in Eastern Indonesia is prevalent, diverse and severe: Implications for primaquine therapy against relapsing vivax malaria. *PLoS Negl. Trop Dis.* 2015, **9**: e0003602. [Doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0003602](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0003602)

24. Satyagraha AW, Sadhewa A, Elvira R, Elyazar I *et al.*: Assessment of point-of-care diagnostics for G6PD deficiency in malaria endemic rural Eastern Indonesia. *PLoS Negl. Trop. Dis.* 2016, **19**: e0004457. [Doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0004457](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0004457)
25. Satyagraha AW, Sadhewa A, Panggalo LV, Subekti D *et al.*: Genotypes and phenotypes of G6PD deficiency among Indonesian females across diagnostic thresholds of G6PD activity

guiding safe primaquine therapy of latent malaria. *PLoS Negl. Trop. Dis.* 2021, **15**: e0009610.
[Doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0009610](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0009610)

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